

Effect of External Magnetic Field on Material Removal Rate and Tool Wear Rate During Electrical Discharge Machining of UNS S41000 Stainless Steel

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ABSTRACT

EDM is a widely used non-conventional machining process in which material is removed from both the workpiece and the tool through melting and vaporization. During this process, a portion of the molten material resolidifies on the surfaces, while the remaining material forms debris within the machining gap. This debris can lead to unstable conditions, including uncontrolled secondary sparking, which adversely affects the workpiece surface quality and reduces machining efficiency.

To overcome this issue, an external magnetic field is introduced to assist in the rapid removal of debris and prevent particle accumulation in the machining gap. In this study, a copper tool is used to machine an UNS S41000 workpiece under both magnetic field-assisted and conventional EDM conditions. The experimental design is developed using the Taguchi method to minimize the number of experiments while effectively studying the influence of process parameters. An L9 orthogonal array is employed, with voltage, current, and pulse-on time selected as input parameters to evaluate their effect on MRR and TWR. The results are further analyzed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to determine the significance of each parameter. The findings indicate that EDM with an applied magnetic field performs better than conventional EDM, as it enhances debris removal, improves machining stability, and increases overall machining efficiency. This report presents an experimental investigation on the effects of an external magnetic field on the Material Removal Rate (MRR) and Tool Wear Rate (TWR) in Electrical Discharge Machining (EDM).

INTRODUCTION

INTRODUCTION TO NON-TRADITIONAL MACHINING PROCESS

Non-traditional manufacturing processes refer to a group of advanced machining methods in which excess material is removed using mechanical, thermal, electrical, chemical energy, or a combination of these, without the use of a conventional sharp cutting tool as in traditional machining processes. These processes are widely used in technologically advanced industries such as aeronautics, automobiles, nuclear reactors, missiles, and turbines, where components are often made from high-strength, temperature-resistant alloys that possess excellent properties like corrosion resistance, toughness, and high strength. With the rapid advancement of materials technology, there is a growing need for suitable machining processes capable of efficiently and safely processing such advanced materials while ensuring high productivity, accuracy, and automation. Extremely hard, brittle, and difficult-to-machine materials cannot be effectively processed using conventional methods such as turning, drilling, shaping, and milling. Non-traditional or advanced machining processes are therefore employed when conventional methods become impractical, uneconomical, or incapable of producing the required geometry, especially in cases involving very hard materials, fragile components, slender or flexible workpieces, or highly complex shapes. These processes offer significant advantages when applied appropriately to meet demanding machining requirements.

ELECTRICAL DISCHARGE MACHINE

Electrical Discharge Machining (EDM) is one of the most widely used non-traditional material removal processes. In EDM, material is removed through a series of controlled electrical discharges occurring between the tool electrode and the workpiece, with no direct physical contact between them. The process uses electrical sparks as the cutting mechanism to erode material and produce components of the desired shape. Material removal occurs by applying a high-frequency pulsating (ON/OFF) electrical current through the electrode, which generates repeated sparks that melt and vaporize minute portions of the workpiece in a controlled manner.

WORKING PRINCIPLE OF EDM

The basic principle of Electrical Discharge Machining (EDM) is the conversion of electrical energy into thermal energy through a series of discrete electrical discharges occurring between the electrode and the workpiece, both of which are immersed in a dielectric fluid. The dielectric plays an important role by providing insulation and preventing electrolysis between the electrodes during the machining process. A spark is generated at the point of minimum inter-electrode gap when the applied high voltage overcomes the dielectric strength of the fluid, leading to breakdown and the formation of a plasma channel. This localized discharge produces extremely high temperatures, typically in the range of 8,000 to 12,000°C, resulting in the erosion of material from both the workpiece and the tool electrode. Each spark has a very short duration, and the entire cycle occurs within a few microseconds. Following each discharge, a rapid drop in temperature causes the surrounding dielectric fluid to cool the region and flush away the molten material from the machining zone in the form of fine microscopic debris.

MECHANISM OF MATERIAL REMOVAL

The electro-sparking method of metal working is based on an electric erosion process in which material removal from the electrode is achieved through controlled electrical discharges. These discharges are initiated by the ionization of the dielectric medium, where its molecules break down into ions and electrons. The discharge occurs between two electrodes immersed in either a gaseous or liquid medium when a suitable voltage is applied across them. As the electric field intensity builds up to a critical level, electrons are emitted from the anode surface under the influence of the field force. These electrons then travel across the inter-electrode gap, colliding with neutral dielectric molecules and further generating ions and free electrons, thereby sustaining the ionization process.

At a certain point, the ionization becomes sufficient to form a narrow, continuously conductive channel between the electrodes. Once this channel is established, a momentary high-current discharge flows through it, producing a sudden release of energy. This energy results in extremely high temperatures within the plasma channel, leading to localized melting and vaporization of material from both the workpiece and the tool electrode. As a result, a small crater is formed at the discharge site on the workpiece surface.

The eroded particles from both the tool and workpiece are then quenched in the dielectric fluid, where they cool and form a colloidal suspension. These suspended particles, along with decomposition products of the dielectric, are drawn into the inter-electrode gap during the early stage of the discharge process. They align along the electric field lines, forming temporary conductive bridges. Subsequent discharges occur preferentially along these bridges due to enhanced ionization, continuing the material removal process.

1.1 SINKER EDM

Sinker EDM, also known as cavity type EDM or volume EDM, is a machining process in which both the electrode and the workpiece are submerged in an insulating liquid such as oil or another dielectric fluid. The electrode and workpiece are connected to a suitable power supply that creates an electrical potential between them. As the electrode gradually approaches the workpiece, dielectric breakdown occurs in the fluid, forming an ionization channel and generating a series of small electrical sparks. The heat produced by these sparks, along with localized cavitation effects, vaporizes material from the workpiece and, to a lesser extent, from the electrode. These discharges occur in large numbers at random locations across the machining gap. As material is eroded from the workpiece, the spark gap increases, and the machine automatically lowers the electrode to maintain a constant discharge distance, allowing the process to continue continuously. Several hundred thousand sparks may occur per second, and the process is controlled by carefully regulated parameters known as “on time” and “off time.” The on-time determines the duration of each spark; a longer on-time results in deeper material removal per discharge and produces a rougher surface finish, while a shorter on-time improves surface quality. The off-time represents the interval between successive sparks and allows the dielectric fluid to flush

away eroded debris through a nozzle, preventing short circuits and ensuring stable machining. These time settings are typically measured in microseconds. The workpiece is shaped by replication of the electrode geometry, while a numerical control system continuously monitors the spark gap conditions such as voltage and current, and coordinates the movement of machine axes along with the pulse generator. The dielectric fluid is also filtered to remove debris particles and decomposition products, ensuring consistent machining performance.

Table
Figure 1.1 Sinker EDM

1.1 EDM PROCESS PARAMETERS:

1.1.1 Polarity

The Polarity normally used is normal polarity in which the tool is negative, and workpiece is positive. In case of positive polarity, tool is positive and workpiece is negative. In general, polarity is determined by experiments and is a matter of tool material, work material and current .

1.6.2 Pulse on Time

Pulse on-time refers to the duration during which the actual machining or spark discharge takes place. The Material Removal Rate (MRR) is directly proportional to the energy supplied during

this period. The spark energy is governed by the peak current and the length of the on-time. When the on-time is increased, more energy is delivered to the workpiece, resulting in greater material erosion. This produces larger and deeper craters, which in turn leads to a rougher surface finish. Higher on-time also increases the heat input to the workpiece, causing a thicker recast layer and a deeper heat-affected zone. Therefore, excessively high on-time values can be counterproductive, and beyond an optimum level for a given electrode–workpiece combination, the material removal rate may start to decrease.

1.6.3 Pulse off Time

Pulse off-time is the interval during which the dielectric medium regains its insulating properties by de-ionization of the spark gap. After each discharge, the gap becomes ionized, and sufficient time is required before the next spark can occur. During off-time, the power supply is switched off to allow the dielectric to recover its strength. If the off-time is too short, it may lead to unstable machining conditions such as short circuits or arcing. Conversely, if the off-time is too long, the overall machining time increases since no material removal occurs during this period. Thus, each EDM cycle consists of carefully controlled on-time and off-time durations, typically measured in microseconds, to ensure stable and efficient machining.

1.6.4 Current

Current in EDM refers to the electrical power used during the discharge process and is measured in amperes. It is one of the most significant machining parameters affecting performance. During each on-time pulse, the current rises until it reaches a preset peak value, known as the peak current. Higher peak current results in increased energy per spark, which enhances material removal rate but also produces larger craters on the workpiece surface. As a result, higher current improves machining speed but leads to a rougher surface finish and increased tool wear.

1.6.5 Gap Voltage

Gap voltage is the electrical potential difference maintained between the tool electrode and the workpiece. The energy of each spark is influenced by the applied voltage, which in turn determines the inter-electrode gap controlled by the servo system. A larger gap voltage increases the spacing between the electrodes, improving the flushing of debris from the machining zone and stabilizing subsequent discharges, thereby enhancing material removal rate. However, excessive voltage can degrade surface finish due to larger crater formation. The voltage at which discharge actually occurs is known as the discharge voltage, which depends on the dielectric strength and the distance between the electrodes.

1.1.1 Electrode material

- 2 Electrode materials used in EDM can be broadly classified into metallic materials such as copper, brass, tungsten, and aluminium; non-metallic materials such as graphite; combined materials like copper–graphite; and metallic coatings on insulating substrates such as copper-coated plastic or ceramic. The selection of tool electrode material is based on desirable properties such as a high melting point, good electrical conductivity, low wear rate, and ease of machinability. Additionally, the material should be economical and easily shaped using conventional manufacturing methods. High-density graphite is commonly used in pulsed EDM systems due to its high melting temperature, which results in low electrode wear. Copper is also widely used because it supports high material removal rates and remains stable under sparking conditions.

In contrast, brass exhibits comparatively higher tool wear. Advanced materials such as copper–boron and silver–tungsten show very low wear characteristics, while copper–tungsten electrodes, often used as cathodes, provide high machining rates along with minimal wear. However, due to their high cost and difficulty in machining into complex shapes, their applications are somewhat limited.

Type of flushing

The dielectric fluid must be circulated freely between Tool and Work Material. It is basic requirement of dielectric that it should maintain its dielectric strength (insulating properties) during its whole operation. There is no problem at the start of EDM, but after discharge the debris are produced in the gap reduce the dielectric strength, which cause unwanted discharges and can damage both tool and workpiece. Hence effective flushing is required to remove unwanted debris from the gap. TWR and MRR are affected by the type of dielectric and the method of its flushing.

Type of Dielectric

Dielectric medium acts as an insulator medium which doesn't conduct electricity and used to flush the eroded particles. And it cools region, tool and work material. Paraffin, White Spirit, Kerosene, deionized water, hydrocarbon fluids, EDM oil and transformer oil are the different EDM dielectric fluids.

1.2 PERFORMANCE MEASURES

1.2.1 Material Removal Rate (MRR).

The material removal rate is defined as the amount of material removed from the workpiece per unit time. The material removal rate can be calculated from the volume of material removal or from the weight difference of work piece before and after machining. It is an indication of how fast or slow the machining rate is and an important performance parameter in EDM, as this is usually a very slow process. Higher machining productivity must also be achieved with a desired accuracy and surface finish. The MRR greatly depends on the process parameters. A higher value of discharging voltage, peak current, pulse duration, duty cycle, and lower values of pulse interval can result in higher MRR. In addition to these electrical parameters, other nonelectrical

parameters and material properties have significant influence on MRR.

$$\text{MRR}(\text{gm}/\text{min}) = \frac{\text{Initial weight of the w/p} - \text{final weight of the w/p}}{\text{time}}$$

1.1.1 Tool Wear Rate (TWR):

The tool wear rate is defined as the amount of tool wore from the workpiece per unit time. The Tool wear rate can be calculated from the volume of tool wore or from the weight difference of tool before and after machining. Tool wear is related to the melting point of the materials. The ability of a tool material to produce and maintain detail is directly related to its resistance to wear and its machinability .TWR is expressed as the ratio of the difference of weight of the tool before & after machining to the machining time. It follows that if an electrode can successfully resist erosion at its most corner points, then overall wear will be minimized, and maximum electrode life achieved.

$$\text{TWR}(\text{gm}/\text{min}) = \frac{\text{Initial weight of the tool} - \text{final weight of the tool}}{\text{time}}$$

LITERATURE REVIEW

A significant amount of research has been carried out on various aspects of Electrical Discharge Machining (EDM), particularly focusing on different materials, tool electrodes, and optimization of process parameters to enhance machine performance and efficiency. G. Anand et al. [1] conducted experiments on HCHCr steel using magnetic field-assisted EDM and Grey Relational Analysis to determine optimal process parameters. Their results showed that the presence of a magnetic field improved material removal rate (MRR) and reduced surface roughness compared to conventional EDM. Similarly, Govindan et al. [2] studied dry EDM with single-spark conditions under a magnetic field and reported an increase in MRR due to the Lorentz force generated by the magnetic field. Vignesh S. Naidu et al. [3] investigated electromagnetic field-assisted EDM on Ti-6Al-4V and observed a significant improvement in MRR over conventional EDM.

Krishan Kant [4] performed experiments on En-19 tool steel considering output parameters such as MRR, tool wear rate, and overcut, and optimized machining conditions by varying current, powder concentration in dielectric, tool material, and pulse-on time with and without magnetic field assistance. Ahsan A. Khan et al. [5] studied SUS 304 stainless steel under an electromagnetic field and found that magnetic field application and duty factor significantly influenced surface roughness at different peak current levels. A.M. Efendee et al. [6] investigated the effect of magnetic polarity in magnetic field-assisted EDM on tool steel and concluded that better surface finish was achieved compared to conventional EDM, with the north-to-south pole arrangement providing optimal results for improved machining quality.

T. A. El-Taweel et al. [7] conducted experiments on armoured steel (HV500) using copper and graphite electrodes and found that MRR increased with higher magnetic flux density and peak current, while lower tool wear rate was achieved at higher magnetic flux density and duty factor combinations. Reza et al. [8] studied the relationship between discharge energy and MRR in magnetic field-assisted EDM and observed that MRR increased with higher discharge energy due to greater thermal input to the machining zone. In another study, Reza Teimouri and Hamid Baseri [9] investigated SPK cold work steel using copper electrodes and reported that applying a rotational magnetic field increased tool wear rate and overcut, while tool rotation negatively affected overcut. Yan-Cherng Lin and Ho-Shiun Lee [10] examined SKD 61 steel with electrolytic copper electrodes and analyzed discharge waveforms to evaluate machining stability along with MRR, electrode wear rate, and surface integrity under magnetic force-assisted EDM.

Finally, Ajeet Bergaley and Narendra Sharma [11] studied HCHCr D3 steel using copper electrodes and Taguchi optimization techniques, concluding that MRR is primarily influenced by current, followed by pulse-on time and copper powder concentration in dielectric fluid, while tool wear rate is mainly affected by current and generally decreases with increasing current.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

The steps involved in methodology are:

- Selection of process parameters i.e. voltage, current and pulse on to find its effect on the performance measure such as Material Removal Rate and Tool Wear Rate
- Taguchi method is used for the selection of L9 orthogonal array and assign these parameters to the orthogonal array.

3.2 TAGUCHI METHOD

- Conducting of the experiments based on the arrangement of the orthogonal array.
- Analyse the experimental results using the signal to noise(S/N) ratio and analysis of variance (ANOVA) to find optimal parameters

The effects of input parameters such as voltage, current, and pulse-on time were investigated through experimentation. The performance measures, namely Material Removal Rate (MRR) and Tool Wear Rate (TWR), were evaluated under both the presence and absence of a magnetic field. A total of nine experimental runs were carried out twice based on Taguchi's L9 orthogonal array, once with a magnetic field and once without it. UNS S41000 was selected as the workpiece material, and eighteen specimens were prepared in total, with nine samples machined under magnetic field conditions and the remaining nine under conventional EDM conditions. The

corresponding MRR and TWR values were calculated and systematically tabulated.

Using Taguchi's method, the signal-to-noise (S/N) ratio was determined to evaluate the quality characteristics and to analyze the influence of each selected process parameter on the responses. Furthermore, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed to assess the relative significance of each parameter on both the workpiece and tool, and to identify the most influential factors affecting performance. Based on this statistical approach, optimal process parameters were determined, and the effects of the selected parameters on MRR and TWR were thoroughly analyzed.

TAGUCHI METHOD A scientific approach to planning experiments is essential for conducting efficient and reliable experimental work. Statistical Design of Experiments (DOE) provides a structured methodology for planning experiments so that appropriate data can be collected and analyzed using statistical techniques, leading to valid and objective conclusions. In experimental studies where data are influenced by random errors, statistical methods offer the only objective means of analysis. Therefore, an experimental investigation consists of two closely related aspects: the design of experiments and the statistical analysis of the resulting data, as the choice of analysis technique depends on the experimental design adopted.

Design of Experiments (DOE) is a branch of applied statistics that focuses on planning, conducting, analyzing, and interpreting controlled experiments to determine the influence of various factors on one or more response variables. It is a powerful tool that allows multiple input parameters to be varied systematically in order to study their effect on desired outputs. The key advantages of DOE include a significant reduction in the number of experimental trials, identification of critical process variables that influence performance, determination of optimal parameter settings, qualitative assessment of factors, and estimation of experimental error.

In the present work, Taguchi's method has been employed to design the experiments, and the collected data have been analyzed using statistical techniques. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is used to evaluate the relative significance of control factors on machined surface quality and to identify the most influential parameters. It is also applied to determine the optimal levels of process parameters and to study their effect on Material Removal Rate (MRR) and Tool Wear Rate (TWR).

EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN STRATEGY

Taguchi recommends the use of orthogonal arrays (OA) for the layout of experiments, as they provide an efficient and systematic approach to experimental design. Designing an experiment

involves selecting the most suitable orthogonal array and assigning the parameters and their interactions to the appropriate columns. The use of linear graphs and triangular tables, as suggested by Taguchi, simplifies the assignment of factors, ensuring a structured experimental setup. This approach ensures that all experiments are designed in a consistent manner, leading to comparable and reliable results.

In the Taguchi method, experimental results are analyzed to achieve key objectives such as determining the optimum condition for a process or product, estimating the contribution of individual parameters and their interactions, and predicting the response under optimal conditions. The optimal setting is identified by analyzing the main effects of each parameter, which represent the overall trend of influence on the response. Understanding the contribution of each factor is essential for implementing effective process control in manufacturing operations.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is commonly used in Taguchi-based studies to determine the percentage contribution of each parameter at a specified confidence level. The ANOVA table helps identify which parameters significantly influence the process and require strict control. Taguchi proposes two approaches for data analysis: the standard approach, where results from single or repeated trials are analyzed using main effects and ANOVA, and the second approach, which utilizes the Signal-to-Noise (S/N) ratio, especially for multiple runs. The S/N ratio is a performance measure linked to the loss function and is used to identify robust operating conditions by minimizing variability in the response. By maximizing the S/N ratio, process losses can be reduced, ensuring more stable performance. Taguchi also recommends the use of outer arrays to intentionally introduce noise factors into experiments, allowing the study of variability under realistic operating conditions, as real-world processes are often influenced by multiple interacting noise factors.

ORTHOGONAL ARRAY

Orthogonal Arrays (OAs) play a crucial role in achieving the high efficiency of the Taguchi method. They are derived from factorial designs of experiments using advanced mathematical concepts such as combinatorics, finite fields, geometry, and error-correcting codes. These algorithms ensure that orthogonal arrays are constructed in a statistically independent manner, where each level of a factor appears an equal number of times within a column. Additionally, for any given level in one column, all levels of other columns also occur equally often, ensuring mutual orthogonality among columns.

A variety of orthogonal arrays with different numbers of factors and levels are available within the Taguchi method. Since each column is orthogonal to the others, any significant difference in response between levels of a particular factor indicates that the factor has a strong influence on the quality characteristic being studied. This is because the effects of other factors are evenly distributed and do not bias the results. As a result, the Taguchi method provides consistency in experimental design and analysis while significantly reducing experimental time and cost.

SIGNAL TO NOISE RATIO

Once the experimental design has been determined and the trials have

been carried out, the measured performance characteristic from each trial can be used to analyse the relative effect of the different parameters. The process design phase involves deciding the best values/levels for the control factors. The signal to noise (S/N) ratio is an ideal metric for that purpose. A high value of S/N implies that signal is much higher than the random effects of noise factors. Process operation consistent with highest S/N always yields optimum quality with minimum variation.

1. Larger is better:

$$(S/N)_{HB} = -10 \log (MSD_{HB})$$

Where,

$$MSD_{HB} = (1/n) * (1/y_1^2 + 1/y_2^2 + \dots + 1/y_n^2)$$

n = no. of repetitions,

y= observed value.

This S/N Ratio is chosen for performance measure MRR

2. Smaller is better:

$$(S/N)_{LB} = -10 \log (MSD_{LB})$$

Where,

$$MSD_{LB} = (1/n) * (1/y_1^2 + 1/y_2^2 + \dots + 1/y_n^2)$$

This S/N Ratio is chosen for performance measure TWR

3. Nominal is best

$$(S/N)_{NB} = 10 * \log_{10} [(mean^2) / variance]$$

This case arises when a specified value is MOST desired, meaning that neither a smaller nor a larger value is desirable.

It is to be mentioned that for nominal the best type of characteristic, the standard definition of MSD has been used. For smaller the better type the target value is zero. For larger the better type, the inverse of each large value becomes a small value and again the target value is zero. Therefore, for all the three expressions the smallest magnitude of MSD is being sought. The constant 10 has been purposely used to magnify S/N number for each analysis and negative sign is used to set S/N ratio of larger the better relative to the square deviation of smaller the better.

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3.3 TAGUCHI DESIGN STEP

- Selection of process parameters and identification of responses,
- Assignment of levels to the process parameters,
- Selection of proper Orthogonal Array(OA) and assignment of process parameters to the O.A,
- Experiment is to be conducted based on orthogonal array,
- Calculation of loss function and the S/N ratio,
- Calculation of mean S/N ratio and analyse the results,

IMPLEMENTATION

4.1 INTRODUCTION

The effect of input parameters i.e. voltage, current and pulse on are investigated through the experimentation. The performance measures MRR and TWR are determined in the presence and absence of magnetic field. The assignment of factors is carried out using statistical software MINITAB. A standard Taguchi L9 Orthogonal Array (OA) is chosen for this investigation as it can accommodate three parameters with each at three levels evaluated independently. The L9 Orthogonal Array (OA) is selected two times to do the experiments in which one L9 OA is used to conduct the experiment in the presence of magnetic field and another in the absence of magnetic field After conducting 18 experiments, the values of MRR and TWR is tabulated in the table

4.2 EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

An L9 Orthogonal Array (OA) was selected for the experimentation to study the effects of control factors such as voltage (V), current (I), and pulse-on time (Ton) on the Material Removal Rate (MRR) and Tool Wear Rate (TWR) under both the presence and absence of a magnetic field. The parameters and their levels used in the study are presented in Table 4.2, while the experimental design based on the L9 OA is shown in Table 4.6.

The experiments were conducted using an Electrical Discharge Machine, whose specifications are provided in Table 4.1. Stainless steel grade UNS S41000, with a density of 7800 kg/m³, was selected as the workpiece material. Each workpiece was prepared by facing and grinding to a cylindrical shape of 20 mm diameter and 16 mm height prior to experimentation, as shown in Figure 4.1. Copper, with a density of 8960 kg/m³, was chosen as the electrode material, having dimensions of 20 mm diameter and 30 mm height to accommodate the machining depth and proper clamping, as illustrated in Figure 4.2. The material properties of both workpiece and tool are provided in Tables 4.3, 4.4, and 4.5. In the setup, the tool was connected to the negative terminal and the workpiece to the positive terminal.

Neodymium magnets (N35) were used to generate an external magnetic field of 2.4 Tesla, with the schematic arrangement shown in Figures 4.6 and 4.7. Grade A EDM oil was used as the dielectric fluid. The machining time varied for each experimental run, and parameters such as voltage, current, and pulse-on time were set at different levels according to the L9 orthogonal array.

- 5 A total of eighteen workpieces were machined, where nine samples were processed in the presence of a magnetic field and the remaining nine without it. The machined specimens under both conditions are shown in Figures 4.3 and 4.4. The magnets were arranged in an N–S configuration around the workpiece to create an attractive magnetic field, ensuring that the magnetic flux acted perpendicular to the electrode. This configuration enhances ionization by influencing the motion of charged particles, thereby improving the discharge process. The resulting magnetic field promotes better removal of electrons and ions from their atomic structure, increasing ionization and machining efficiency. The machining performance was evaluated in terms of Material Removal Rate (MRR in g/min) and Tool Wear Rate (TWR in g/min) to assess the influence of the selected parameters under both conditions.

6 *Table 4.1 Specifications of machine*

7

Specifications	Range	Units
Table dimension	750*500	mm
Work tank dimension	1000*600*500	mm
X Travel	500	mm
Y Travel	350	mm
Z Travel	300	mm
Max table loading	1000	KGS

Dielectric Capacity	600	LTS
Normal current	100/200	AMPS

Table 4.2 Parameters and levels used in the experiment

	PARAMETERS	LEVELS		
		1	2	3
A	Voltage	32	33	34
B	Current	10	15	20
C	Pulse on	500	900	1000

Table 4.3 Material used in the experiment

S.no	Material Used	Material	Dimension
1	Work piece	UNSS41000 i.e. Stainless Steel - Grade 410	16mm height and 20mm diameter
2	Electrode	Copper	30mm height and 20mm diameter
3	Magnets	Neodymium Magnet N35	30*10*5mm

Table 4.4 Physical properties of UNSS41000

Density	7.74 gm/cm ³
Electrical resistivity at 210°C	57 μΩ.cm
Thermal conductivity at 500°C	28.7 W/m.K
Coefficient of thermal expansion at (0-649°C)	11.6 μm/m/K
Modulus of elasticity	200 GPa
Specific heat at (0-100°C)	0.46kJ/kg/K

Table 4.5 Main properties of copper tool.

Density	8.96 gm/cm ³
Electrical Resistivity at 20 °C	1.673 μΩ-cm
Thermal Conductivity	401 W/m/K

Melting Point	1085 °C
Specific Heat	0.39 kJ/kg K
Young's Modulus	110–128 GPa

Figure 4.1 Cross section of work piece

Figure 4.2 Cross section of Copper tool

Figure 4.3 Work pieces machined in the presence of magnetic field

Figure 4.4 Work pieces machined in the absence of magnetic field

Figure 4.5 Fixture set up in EDM machine

Figure 4.6 Experimental layout with external magnetic field

Figure 4.7 Side view of experimental layout with external magnetic field The effect of parameters is investigated through experimentation and performance measures like material removal rate and tool wear rate are calculated. The metal removal rate is calculated by the following equation.

$$\text{MRR} = \frac{W_b - W_a}{t}$$

t

Where

W_b : Workpiece weight before machining in grams.

W_a : Workpiece weight after machining in grams.

The tool wear rate is calculated by the following equation.

$$\text{TWR} = \frac{T_b - T_a}{t}$$

Where

T_b : Tool weight before machining in grams.

T_a : Tool weight after machining in grams.

The experiments are conducted according to Taguchi L9 orthogonal array shown in the table 4.6 . After conducting 18 experiments in which nine experiments are conducted in the presence of magnetic field and nine experiments in the absence of magnetic field, the values of MRR and TWR are tabulated in Table 4.7 and Table 4.8 respectively

Table 4.6 L9 Orthogonal array of parameters

Exp No	Voltage	Current	Pulse on
	V	C	Ton
1	32	10	500
2	32	15	900
3	32	20	1000
4	33	10	900
5	33	15	1000
6	33	20	500
7	34	10	1000

8	34	15	500
9	34	20	900

Table 4.7 Values of MRR and TWR in the presence of magnetic field

Exp No	Voltage	Current	Pulse on μ sec	with magnets	
				MRR (gm/min)	TWR(gm/min)
1	32	10	500	0.07482679	0.006928406
2	32	15	900	0.261068702	0.013740458
3	32	20	1000	0.119349005	0.008679928
4	33	10	900	0.16119403	0.013432836
5	33	15	1000	0.1104	0.00864
6	33	20	500	0.132754881	0.013015184
7	34	10	1000	0.038946015	0.003084833
8	34	15	500	0.092675159	0.008598726
9	34	20	900	0.244444444	0.02

Table 4.8 Values of MRR and TWR in the absence of magnetic field

Exp No	Voltage	Current	Pulse on Ton	without magnets	
				MRR(gm/min)	TWR(gm/min)
1	32	10	500	0.070474138	0.006465517
2	32	15	900	0.090487239	0.012529002
3	32	20	1000	0.103020668	0.007631161
4	33	10	900	0.168932039	0.02038835
5	33	15	1000	0.099854015	0.010510949
6	33	20	500	0.119092628	0.011342155
7	34	10	1000	0.051762941	0.0036009
8	34	15	500	0.088159772	0.009415121
9	34	20	900	0.215384615	0.017307692

Taguchi method is used to study the response variation using signal to noise ratio. The material removal rate is considered as quality characteristic with the concept of “Larger the better” and tool wear rate is considered as quality characteristic with the concept of

“Smaller the better”.

The S/N Ratio chosen for performance measure MRR is,

Larger is better:

$$(S/N)_{HB} = -10 \log (\text{MSD}_{HB})$$

Where,

$$\text{MSD}_{HB} = \frac{1}{n} \left(\frac{1}{y_1^2} + \frac{1}{y_2^2} + \dots + \frac{1}{y_n^2} \right)$$

n = no. of repetitions,

y = observed value.

The S/N Ratio chosen for performance measure TWR is, Smaller is better:

$$(S/N)_{LB} = -10 \log (\text{MSD}_{LB})$$

$$\text{Where, MSD}_{LB} = \frac{1}{n} (y_1^2 + y_2^2 + y_3^2 + \dots + y_n^2)$$

The results are converted to S/N ratio for further calculation and analysis. Performance characteristics now depend on S/N ratio. For better performance higher material removal rate and lower the tool wear is efficient. Hence, here MRR lie in the larger the better category of S/N ratio and EWR lie in smaller the better S/N ratio. The S/N ratio of MRR and TWR in the presence of magnetic field are calculated and shown in the table 4.9 and in the absence of magnetic field are shown in the table 4.10

Table 4.9 S/N ratios of MRR and TWR in the presence of magnetic field

	With magnets	
Exp no	S/N MRR	S/N TWR
1	-22.5189	43.18733
2	-11.6649	37.23998
3	-18.4636	41.22968
4	-15.853	37.43665
5	-19.1406	41.26973
6	-17.539	37.71099
7	-28.1907	50.21537
8	-20.6607	41.31132
9	-12.2364	33.9794

Table 4.10 S/N ratios of MRR and TWR in the absence magnetic field

	Without magnets	
Exp no	S/N MRR	S/N MRR
1	-23.0394	-23.0394
2	-20.8683	-20.8683
3	-19.7415	-19.7415
4	-15.4458	-15.4458
5	-20.0127	-20.0127
6	-18.4823	-18.4823
7	-25.7196	-25.7196
8	-21.0946	-21.0946
9	-13.3357	-13.3357

After determining the S/N ratio, analysis of variance is done to find the optimal

process parameter levels and to analyse the effect of these parameters on metal removal rate and tool wear rate values. The percentage contribution of each parameter is calculated to find its significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

5.1 INTRODUCTION

The effect of magnetic assisted electrical discharge machining is analyzed on Material Removal Rate (MRR) and Tool Wear Rate (TWR) with and without using external magnetic field. The machining parameters, such as voltage (v), current (I), pulse on (Ton), are arranged according to Taguchi L9 orthogonal array.

Using the Taguchi method and ANOVA, the results of the experiments are analysed to achieve optimum condition and to estimate the contribution of individual parameters.

Design of Experiments (DOE) helps to investigate the effects of input variables (parameters) on an output variable (response). Here the input variables are voltage, current and pulse on. Data are collected at each run and the output variables are MRR and TWR. The results of MRR and TWR are shown in Table 5.1

Table 5.1 Values of MRR and TWR in the presence and absence of magnetic field

Exp No	Voltage	Current	Pulse on	with magnets		without magnets	
				MRR(gm/min)	TWR(gm/min)	MRR(gm/min)	TWR(gm/min)
1	32	10	500	0.07482679	0.006928406	0.070474138	0.006465517
2	32	15	900	0.261068702	0.013740458	0.090487239	0.012529002
3	32	20	1000	0.119349005	0.008679928	0.103020668	0.007631161
4	33	10	900	0.16119403	0.013432836	0.168932039	0.02038835
5	33	15	1000	0.1104	0.00864	0.099854015	0.010510949
6	33	20	500	0.132754881	0.013015184	0.119092628	0.011342155
7	34	10	1000	0.038946015	0.003084833	0.051762941	0.0036009
8	34	15	500	0.092675159	0.008598726	0.088159772	0.009415121
9	34	20	900	0.244444444	0.02	0.215384615	0.017307692

The results are converted to S/N ratio for further calculation and analysis. Performance characteristics now depend on S/N ratio. For better performance higher material removal rate and lower the tool wear is efficient. Hence, here MRR lie in the larger

the better category of S/N ratio and EWR lie in smaller the better S/N ratio. The S/N ratio of MRR and TWR calculated are shown in the table 5.2

Table 5.2 Values of S/N ratio of MRR and TWR in the presence and absence of magnetic field

Exp no	With magnets		Without magnets	
	S/N MRR	S/N TWR	S/N MRR	S/N TWR
1	-22.5189	43.18733	-23.0394	43.78793
2	-11.6649	37.23998	-20.8683	38.04167
3	-18.4636	41.22968	-19.7415	42.34819
4	-15.853	37.43665	-15.4458	33.81236
5	-19.1406	41.26973	-20.0127	39.56716
6	-17.539	37.71099	-18.4823	38.90609
7	-28.1907	50.21537	-25.7196	48.87178
8	-20.6607	41.31132	-21.0946	40.52348
9	-12.2364	33.9794	-13.3357	35.23522

5.1 Effect of MRR in the presence of magnetic field

The main effect of S/N ratio of MRR in the presence of magnetic field is shown in the Figure 5.1 and Response table for S/N ratio of MRR in the presence of magnetic field is shown in the table 5.3

Figure 5.1 S/N ratio of MRR in the presence of magnetic field

Table 5.3 Response table for S/N ratio of MRR in the presence of magnetic field

Level	voltage	current	pulse on
1	-17.55	-22.19	-20.24
2	-17.51	-17.16	-13.25
3	-20.36	-16.08	-21.93
Delta	2.85	6.11	8.68
Rank	3	2	1

Table 5.4 ANOVA of MRR in the presence of magnetic field

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value	contribution%
voltage	2	0.001073	0.000537	1.43	0.411	2.44
current	2	0.009548	0.004774	12.74	0.073	21.7
pulse on	2	0.032633	0.016316	43.56	0.022	74.2
Error	2	0.000749	0.000375			1.7
Total	8	0.044004				

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) of MRR in the presence of magnetic field is done and contribution percentage of each parameter is determined. The analysis of variance is shown in the table 5.4. It is observed that pulse on is the significant factor for altering MRR and the contribution percentage of voltage, current and pulse on is 2.44 %, 21.7%, 74.2% respectively.

5.2 Effect of TWR in the presence of magnetic field

The main effect of S/N ratio of TWR in the presence of magnetic field is shown in the Figure 5.2 and Response table for S/N ratio of TWR in the presence of magnetic field is shown in the table 5.5

Figure 5.2 S/N ratio of TWR in the presence of magnetic field

Table 5.5 Response table for S/N ratio of TWR in the presence of magnetic field

Level	voltage	current	pulse on
1	40.55	43.61	40.74
2	38.81	39.94	36.22
3	41.84	37.64	44.24
Delta	3.03	5.97	8.02
Rank	3	2	1

Analysis of variance(ANOVA) of TWR in the presence of magnetic field is done and contribution percentage of each parameter is determined. The analysis of variance is shown in the table 5.6 .

Table 5.6 ANOVA of TWR in the presence of magnetic field

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value	contribution%
voltage	2	0.000006	0.000003	0.87	0.533	3.09
current	2	0.000056	0.000028	8.83	0.102	28.9
pulse on	2	0.000126	0.000063	19.77	0.048	64.9
Error	2	0.000006	0.000003			3.09
Total	8	0.000194				

It is observed that pulse on is the significant factor for altering TWR and the contribution percentage of voltage, current and pulse on is 3.09%, 28.9%, 64.9% respectively.

5.3 Effect of MRR in the absence of magnetic field

The main effect of S/N ratio of MRR in the absence of magnetic field is shown in the Figure 5.3 and Response table for S/N ratio of MRR in the absence of magnetic field is shown in the table 5.7.

*Figure 5.3 S/N ratio of MRR in the absence of magnetic field**Table 5.7 Response table for S/N ratio of MRR in absence magnetic field*

Level	voltage	current	pulse on
1	-21.22	-21.40	-20.87
2	-17.98	-20.66	-16.55
3	-20.05	-17.19	-21.82
Delta	3.24	4.22	5.27
Rank	3	2	1

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) of MRR in the absence of magnetic field is done and contribution percentage of each parameter is determined. The analysis of variance is shown in the table 5.8.

Table 5.8 ANOVA of MRR in the absence of magnetic field

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value	contribution%
voltage	2	0.00275	0.001375	0.96	0.511	13.35
current	2	0.005206	0.002603	1.81	0.356	25.28
pulse on	2	0.009761	0.00488	3.39	0.228	47.4
Error	2	0.002875	0.001438			13.96
Total	8	0.020592				

It is observed that pulse on is the significant factor for altering MRR and the contribution percentage of voltage, current and pulse on is 13.35%, 25.28%, 47.4% respectively.

5.4 Effect of TWR in the absence of magnetic field

The main effect of S/N ratio of TWR in the absence of magnetic field is shown in the Figure 5.4 and Response table for S/N ratio of TWR absence of magnetic field is shown in the table 5.9

Figure 5.4 S/N ratio of TWR in the absence of magnetic field

Table 5.9 Response table for S/N ratio of TWR in the absence of magnetic field

Level	voltage	current	pulse on
1	41.39	42.16	41.07
2	37.43	39.38	35.70
3	41.54	38.83	43.60
Delta	4.11	3.33	7.90
Rank	2	3	1

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) of TWR in the absence of magnetic field is done and contribution percentage of each parameter is determined. The analysis of variance is shown in the table 5.10

Table 5.10 ANOVA of TWR in the absence of magnetic field

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value	Contribution %
voltage	2	0.000044	0.000022	2.57	0.28	20
current	2	0.000006	0.000003	0.34	0.747	2.727
pulse on	2	0.000152	0.000076	8.81	0.102	69.09
Error	2	0.000017	0.000009			7.727
Total	8	0.00022				

It is observed that pulse on is the significant factor for altering TWR and the contribution percentage of voltage, current and pulse on is 20%, 2.727%, 69.09% respectively.

- 1 The application of a magnetic field in EDM was found to be more advantageous compared to conventional EDM without magnetic assistance. It was observed that the Material Removal Rate (MRR) is primarily influenced by pulse-on time in both cases, as current and pulse-on time are directly proportional to the spark discharge energy. Therefore, an increase in current and pulse-on time leads to higher spark energy, which in turn enhances the MRR. In the case of magnetic field-assisted EDM, a higher MRR was obtained compared to conventional EDM. This improvement is attributed to the effective removal of debris from the

machining gap, which prevents particle accumulation and ensures continuous exposure of fresh work material for subsequent discharges, thereby enhancing material erosion.

- 2 Regarding Tool Wear Rate (TWR), only a slight variation was observed in magnetic field-assisted EDM compared to conventional EDM. It was found that TWR is mainly affected by an increase in pulse-on time and a decrease in current. Overall, the application of a magnetic field improves the machining process by increasing MRR while maintaining or slightly improving TWR characteristics. The optimal parameter settings for MRR under both magnetic and non-magnetic conditions are presented in Table 5.11, while the optimal settings for TWR under both conditions are also determined accordingly.

is shown in the table 5.12

Table 5.11 Optimal parameter setting for MRR with and without magnetic field

Voltage	33 V
Current	20 A
Pulse on	900 μ sec

Table 5.12 Optimal parameter setting for TWR with and without magnetic field

Voltage	34 V
Current	10 A
Pulse on	1000 μ sec

CONCLUSION

- Experimental investigation is done on magnetic assisted EDM and here the magnetic force attached to EDM machine helped for driving the machining debris to expel from the machining gap.
- Observation of the EDMed surfaces showed that, those machined under magnetic field have less amount of solidified debris than that of machined EDMed surfaces without magnetic field.
- It is observed that MRR and TWR is mainly affected by pulse on in both presence and absence of magnetic field.
- The presence of magnetic field increased MRR and decreased TWR.
- Based on S/N ratio of MRR ,the optimal machining parameters are obtained at voltage of 33V ,current of 20amps and pulse on of 900 μ sec.
- Based on S/N ratio of TWR ,the optimal machining parameters are obtained at voltage of 34V ,current of 10amps and pulse on of 1000 μ sec.

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